

Long-term sex differences in symptoms and immune profile in long COVID

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ARTICLE IN PRESS

1 Long-term sex differences in symptoms and immune profile in Long COVID

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25
26 **Abstract**

27 **Background:** Long COVID (LC) is a post-infectious condition affecting millions worldwide,
28 characterized by persistent multisystem symptoms. Females are disproportionately affected,
29 reporting higher symptom burden, particularly neurocognitive and neurosensory complaints.
30 While short-term immunopathology has been described, the long-term clinical course, immune
31 dysregulation, and sex-specific underpinnings remain poorly understood.

32 **Methods:** We analyzed 34 participants experiencing persisting symptoms from 9 months to 5
33 years post-SARS-CoV-2 infection, alongside 26 SARS-CoV-2–infected controls without
34 symptoms. Clinical assessments, symptom inventories, comorbidity analysis, and work
35 capacity evaluation were performed. Immune profiling included flow cytometry of CD4⁺ and
36 CD8⁺ T cells, NK cells, and B cells, as well as quantification of plasma cytokines, soluble
37 factors, and cytotoxic molecules, analyzed in a sex-disaggregated manner.

38 **Results:** Females with LC exhibited higher symptom burden, particularly persistent fatigue,
39 neurocognitive and neurosensory complaints, which increased with age and tended to
40 increase with disease duration, whereas males showed no clear age- or duration-related
41 patterns. Comorbidities, especially affecting endocrine, metabolic, and circulatory systems,
42 were more frequent in females and aligned with symptom severity. Immune profiling revealed
43 subtle but sex-specific differences: females had reduced CD8⁺ T cell cytotoxic profile, lower
44 NKG2D and granzyme K expression, increased sCD40L and sFAS, and decreased perforin,
45 whereas males displayed elevated TNF- α . NK cell function, B cells, and humoral immunity
46 remained largely intact. Over half of participants reported functional impairments affecting
47 work capacity.

48 **Conclusions:** Even though our cohort is small it suggests that prolonged LC is characterized
49 by sex-specific differences in symptom burden and immune profiles. Reduced cytotoxic CD8⁺
50 T cell profile in females may contribute to viral persistence and neurological symptoms,
51 whereas elevated inflammatory markers in males suggest distinct immune pathways. These
52 findings highlight the need for sex- and duration-specific management strategies, the

53 identification of biomarkers, and the development of personalized therapies targeting specific
54 LC endotypes.

55

56 **Plain English summary (250 words)**

57 Long COVID (LC) is a post-infectious condition affecting millions worldwide, marked by
58 persistent, multisystem symptoms, with females disproportionately affected, particularly by
59 neurocognitive and neurosensory complaints. Despite growing knowledge of short-term
60 immune changes, the long-term clinical course, immune dysregulation, and sex-specific
61 mechanisms remain poorly understood. In this study, we analysed 34 LC participants with
62 persisting symptoms from 9 months to 5 years post-SARS-CoV-2 infection and compared
63 them with 26 SARS-CoV-2–infected controls without symptoms. Participants underwent
64 clinical assessment, symptom inventories, comorbidity analysis, and work capacity evaluation,
65 while immune profiling included looking at specific immune cells and proteins in the blood. We
66 looked into differences between males and females. We found that females with LC
67 experienced more symptoms than males, especially fatigue, difficulty concentrating, and
68 memory problems, and these symptoms tended to worsen with age and length of illness.
69 Females also had more underlying health conditions, particularly related to metabolism,
70 neurology, and circulation, which may contribute to their symptoms. Regarding the immune
71 system, females showed changes in immune cells that help fight viruses, which could explain
72 lingering symptoms and vulnerability to neurological issues, while males showed higher levels
73 of general inflammation. More than half of participants reported difficulties with daily activities
74 and work. These findings highlight that LC affects people differently based on sex, illness
75 duration, and health history and underline the need for tailored approaches to treatment, better
76 understanding of the disease, and strategies to support daily functioning and quality of life for
77 those affected.

78

79 **Highlights (<150 words)**

- 80 Prolonged Long COVID (LC) disproportionately affects females, who exhibit higher
81 symptom burden, especially persistent fatigue and neurocognitive complaints,
82 increasing with age and disease duration.
- 83 Females with LC have more comorbidities, particularly in endocrine, metabolic, and
84 circulatory systems, which may exacerbate symptoms through chronic inflammation
85 and organ dysfunction.
- 86 Immune profiling revealed sex-specific alterations: females display reduced CD8⁺ T
87 cell cytotoxicity (lower granzyme K and NKG2D), increased sCD40L and sFAS, and
88 decreased perforin, while males show elevated TNF- α .
- 89 Over half of patients reported functional impairments affecting work capacity,
90 underscoring the socioeconomic burden of LC.
- 91 It emphasizes the need for sex- and duration-specific management strategies for LC.

93 **Keywords**

94 Long COVID; sex differential immunity; long-term symptom persistence; immune
95 dysregulation; cellular and molecular signatures

105 **Background**

106 Five years have passed since the emergence of severe acute respiratory syndrome
107 coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), and COVID-19 continues to pose a global health challenge
108 through Long COVID (LC). The World Health Organization defines LC as a post-infectious
109 condition with symptoms persisting for at least three months after COVID-19 onset, lasting a
110 minimum of two months, and not explained by alternative diagnoses [1–4]. Globally, an
111 estimated 65 million people are affected, with cases rising daily [5–7]. LC presents with a
112 complex, multisystemic symptom profile, encompassing over 100 manifestations that range
113 from mild to profoundly debilitating [8–12], including fatigue, cognitive impairment, respiratory
114 and cardiovascular symptoms [13–21]. These symptoms often impair quality of life, limit daily
115 functioning, and, in many cases, prevent patients from working [13,22]. Although some
116 recover, many individuals have experienced persistent symptoms since early 2020, with
117 neurological sequelae such as brain fog and increased dementia risk reported to last for at
118 least two years [23–31].

119 LC risk factors include female sex, older age, pre-existing comorbidities, ICU admission during
120 acute COVID-19, lower socioeconomic status, and smoking [12,13,32,33]. Biological sex
121 strongly shapes LC presentation, mirroring other post-acute infection syndromes such as
122 myalgic encephalomyelitis/chronic fatigue syndrome (ME/CFS) [34,35]. Unlike acute COVID-
123 19, where males face higher severity and mortality [36–39], LC disproportionately affects
124 females, who report greater fatigue, neurocognitive deficits, headaches, and neurological
125 sequelae, whereas males show more endocrine dysfunction [12,40]. The role of biological sex
126 in LC prevalence, symptomology, and underlying mechanisms has only recently begun to be
127 explored [41,42]. Investigating the cellular and molecular drivers of these sex differences may
128 reveal critical insights into LC pathophysiology and inform precision therapeutic strategies.

129 While the short-term pathophysiology of Long COVID within the first-year post-diagnosis is
130 increasingly understood [43–45], its long-term clinical course, immune alterations, and organ
131 involvement remain largely unknown. Addressing this gap is critical, as LC can last two years
132 or more [46,47] and may, like ME/CFS, become a lifelong condition for some patients. To this

133 end, we analyzed a cohort of 34 participants with LC, experiencing symptoms from 9 months
134 up to 5 years post-infection, and characterized their clinical and immunological profiles in a
135 sex-disaggregated manner.

136

137 **Methods**

138 **Experimental model and subject details**

139 A total of 34 Long COVID (LC) patients and 26 controls were recruited between June 2023
140 and March 2025. All LC patients underwent medical evaluations to exclude alternative medical
141 aetiologies for their persistent symptoms. All participants were recruited at Medical Health
142 Center USF Cuidar Saúde- Seixal. Demographic and clinical characteristics are detailed in
143 Tables S1 and S2.

144 Blood samples were collected by venipuncture in EDTA tubes and were immediately
145 processed. All participants signed the informed consent at the time of enrolment in the study
146 and LC patients completed the clinical survey provided by the Portuguese General Directorate
147 of Health (Direção Geral da Saúde). The survey included questions about COVID-19 data,
148 namely acute disease severity (non-hospitalized or hospitalized), SARS-CoV-2 re-infection,
149 vaccination status (number of doses, date and vaccine brand), employment status post
150 infection and a list of 48 symptoms possible symptoms possible to be reported by LC patients.
151 All procedures were approved by NOVA Medical School ethics committee (178/2024/CEFCM)
152 and by ethics committee for health from ARSLVT (2508/CES/2023), in accordance with the
153 provisions of the Declaration of Helsinki and the Good Clinical Practice guidelines of the
154 International Conference on Harmonization.

155

156 **Inclusion and Exclusion criteria**

157 Inclusion criteria for LC patients were age above 18 years old, previous positive PCR test for
158 SARS-CoV-2 and persistent symptoms for at least 9 months after initial SARS-CoV-2 infection

159 not attributed to any pre-existing comorbidity. Inclusion criteria for control group include age
160 above 18 years and previous positive PCR test for SARS-CoV-2 with no active symptoms post
161 infection.

162 Exclusion criteria for both groups include age below 18 years old and morbid obesity.

163

164 **Blood sample processing**

165 Blood samples were first centrifuged at 1000 x g for 10 minutes to separate the plasma that
166 was carefully removed and stored at -80°C until further analysis. Peripheral blood
167 mononuclear cells (PBMCs) were then isolated by density gradient centrifugation
168 (Lymphosed, Biowest) [48–50] and cultured with RPMI supplemented with 10% FBS and 1%
169 Antimycotic-Antibiotic, at 37°C with 5% of CO₂.

170

171 **Flow cytometry**

172 PBMCs were stained with a fixable viability dye eFluor™ 506 (Invitrogen) and surface labelled
173 with the following antibodies all from BioLegend: anti-CD3 (UCHT1), anti-CD4 (SK3), anti-CD8
174 (SK1), anti-CCR7 (G043H7), anti-CD45RA (HI100), anti-CD56 (HCD56), anti-NKG2D (1D11),
175 anti-CD19 (SJ25C1), anti-CD27 (O323) and anti-CD38 (HIT2). Cells were washed, fixed with
176 1% PFA and permeabilized with Saponin. They were intracellular labelled with the following
177 antibodies all from BioLegend: anti-Perforin (B-D48), anti-Granzyme B (GB11) and anti-
178 Granzyme K (GM26E7). Cells were washed with FACS buffer and acquired in BD LSR
179 Fortessa X-20 and analysed with FlowJo v10.7.3 software (Tree Star).

180

181 **ELISA**

182 Antibody binding to SARS-CoV-2 trimeric spike protein or Nucleocapsid was assessed by a
183 previously described in-house ELISA assay [48,49,51] based on the protocol by Stadlbauer *et*
184 *al* [52]. Briefly, 96-well plates (Nunc) were coated overnight at 4°C with 0.5 µg/ml of trimeric
185 Spike or Nucleocapsid. After blocking with 3% BSA diluted in 0.05% PBS-T, 1:50 diluted

186 plasma was added and incubated for 1 h at room temperature. Plates were washed and
187 incubated for 30 min at room temperature with 1:25,000 dilution of HRP-conjugated anti-
188 human IgA, IgG and IgM antibodies (Abcam, ab97225/ab97215/ab97205). Plates were
189 washed and incubated with TMB substrate (BioLegend), stopped by adding phosphoric acid
190 (Sigma) and read at 450nm. Cut-off for plasma samples resulted from the mean of OD₄₅₀
191 values from negative controls plus 3 times the standard deviation. Endpoint titers were
192 established using a 3-fold dilution series starting at 1:50 and ending at 1:109,350 and defines
193 as the last dilution before the signal dropped below OD₄₅₀ of 0.15. This value was established
194 using plasma from pre-pandemic samples collected from subjects not exposed to SARS-CoV-
195 2. As previously described [51], in each assay we used 6 internal calibrators from 2 high-, 2
196 medium- and 2 low-antibody producers that had been diagnosed for COVID-19 through RT-
197 PCR of nasopharyngeal and/or oropharyngeal swabs. As negative controls, we used pre-
198 pandemic plasma samples collected prior to July 2019.

199

200 **Luminex**

201 Plasma samples were thawed and tested in the LegendPlex Human panel (BioLegend) to
202 quantify the levels of TNF- α , IL-10, perforin, sCD40L, sFAS, Granzyme A, Granzyme B, IL-6,
203 IL-1b, IFN- γ , MCP-1, IL-18, and IL-23. The assay was performed according to manufacturer's
204 instructions and was modified by using half of the amount of all reagents. All plasma samples
205 were diluted 2X with assay buffer, and sample concentrations were calculated according to
206 the dilution factor. Briefly, 12.5 μ l of diluted plasma or standard, and 12.5 μ l of mixed beads
207 were added to each well and incubated for 2 hours. The plate (V-bottom 96 well plate) was
208 washed twice with 100 μ l of wash buffer. Samples and standards were incubated with 12.5 μ l
209 of detection antibody for 1 hour followed by an incubation of 30 minutes with 12.5 μ l of
210 Streptavidin-PE. The plate was washed once, and samples were resuspended in 75 μ l of wash
211 buffer. All incubation steps were performed at room temperature and protected from the light.
212 Samples were acquired in a BD Accuri C6 plus (BD Biosciences) and analyzed with the
213 Windows LegendPlex software (v8.0 BioLegend).

214

215 Statistical Analysis

216 Statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad Prism v9.00 and SPSS v26. First, we
217 tested the normality of the data by using Shapiro Wilk ($n < 6$) or D'Agostino & Pearson ($n > 6$)
218 normality tests, by checking skewness and kurtosis values and visual inspection of data. Then,
219 if the samples followed a normal distribution, we chose the appropriate parametric test;
220 otherwise, the non-parametric counterpart was chosen. In two groups comparisons: for
221 unpaired data, Mann-Whitney test and the unpaired t test were used as indicated in figure
222 legends. Spearman correlation test was used in correlation analysis as described in figure
223 legends. Data represent mean \pm SD for parametric tests, or median \pm IQR for nonparametric
224 tests. p value was considered significant at * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

225 Fisher's Exact Test was used for categorical variables (Table S4). Logistic and Linear
226 Regressions were used to adjust the results for sex, age and time since infection with
227 Bonferroni adjustment (tables S4-S8).

228 To measure the magnitude of the difference, the effect size was calculated as described
229 previously [53,54]. For unpaired t tests: Cohen's d is small if less than 0.3, medium if 0.3 or
230 greater, or large if 0.8 or greater. For Mann-Whitney tests: correlation coefficient r is small if
231 less than 0.3, medium if 0.3 or greater, or large if 0.5 or greater. Effect size values are reported
232 for all figures in tables S9 and S10.

233

234 Results**235 Characterization of the study participants**

236 Our study included 34 Long COVID (LC) patients recruited between June 2023 and March
237 2025, all of whom reported ongoing symptoms, including drowsiness, concentration
238 difficulties, persistent fatigue, and insomnia, between 9 months and 5-years post SARS-CoV-2
239 infection. The cohort comprised 71% females and 29% males (Figure 1A, Table S1), with sex
240 designation assigned by the attending physician based on biological sex at birth. The median
241 age was 53.5 years (interquartile range [IQR] 13), with 4 participants over 70 years of age

242 (Figure 1B, left). Seventy nine percent of patients were white and 21% were black. Only two
243 participants required hospitalization for COVID-19, and one of these required supplemental
244 oxygen (Table S1). The control group comprised 26 SARS-CoV-2–infected individuals without
245 prolonged Long COVID, recruited concurrently with LC patients. The cohort was 73% female
246 and 27% male, with a median age of 51.5 years (IQR 26) (Figure 1A, Table S2).

247 The body mass index (BMI) ranged from 20 to 37.8 in LC patients (median 27.6, IQR 5.8) and
248 24.1 (IQR 5.5) in controls, with no significant differences between groups or by sex (Figure
249 1C–D). Most participants had a single SARS-CoV-2 infection, though LC patients had more
250 positive tests and a longer interval between primary infection and sample collection (Figure
251 1E–F).

252 Regarding COVID-19 vaccination status, two LC patients and two controls had not received
253 any COVID-19 vaccine at the time of sample collection (Tables S1–S2). Among controls, the
254 majority (42%) had received four doses, whereas most LC patients had received two (29%)
255 or three (26%) doses; no significant differences were observed between groups (Figure 1G).
256 The time elapsed between the first vaccine dose and sample collection was also similar across
257 groups (Figure 1H).

258

259 **Females with Long COVID have more underlying health conditions**

260 Comorbidities can impair the body's ability to fight infections, and several studies have
261 reported a higher prevalence of LC in individuals with chronic conditions [12,13,55–57]. Pre-
262 existing comorbidities may also contribute to LC through an associated molecular profile, in
263 which elevated inflammation drives oxidative stress, tissue damage, and organ dysfunction,
264 thereby exacerbating and prolonging symptoms [13]. Nonetheless, we did not find an
265 association between the number of comorbidities and LC status (Table S4). To assess
266 whether comorbidity burden differed in our cohort and whether it was linked to sex, we
267 analyzed the number of comorbidities in each group. We observed that LC patients had more
268 comorbidities than controls (Figure 2A). Sex-disaggregated analysis revealed that this

269 difference was driven by females. Females with LC had more comorbidities than female
270 controls (Figure 2B, left), whereas no differences were observed between males (Figure 2B,
271 right).

272 To analyze participant comorbidities, we classified them into 10 health system categories.
273 Overall, the most common comorbidities in controls were of circulatory system (CS;
274 hypertension 9 participants, 35%), and of the endocrine, metabolic, and nutritional system
275 (EMNS; obesity 6 participants, 23% and overweight 6 participants, 23%) (Table S3). In LC
276 patients, comorbidities of the EMNS (obesity and lipid metabolism disorders, 14 patients each,
277 41%), CS (hypertension, 9 patients, 26%), and psychological conditions (Psy; depression, 8
278 patients, 24%) were the most prevalent (Table S3). A sex disaggregated analysis showed that
279 the frequency of comorbidities is higher in control males than females in all the health system
280 categories (Fig 2C). Curiously, this difference was leveled in LC patients (Fig 2D), with females
281 exhibiting an increase in the frequency of EMNS and Psy comorbidities (Figure 2D).

282

283 **Symptom burden is greater in females with Long COVID.**

284 LC symptoms significantly affect daily living, reducing quality of life and often causing disability
285 [58–60]. We first assessed symptom burden by counting the number of self-reported
286 symptoms per individual and found that females exhibited significantly higher symptom burden
287 than males (Figure 3A). In our cohort, the most frequently reported symptoms were persistent
288 fatigue (76%, 26 patients), drowsiness, concentration problems, and insomnia (71%, 24
289 patients), followed by forgetfulness (68%, 23 patients), dizziness (65%, 22 patients), and
290 anxiety (62%, 21 patients) (Figure S1A, Table S4). Less frequent symptoms, reported by only
291 two patients (6%), included peripheral edema, difficulty urinating, fainting, skin rash,
292 hallucinations and dysmenorrhea (Figure S1A, Table S3).

293 To examine sex differences, symptoms were grouped by health system categories and
294 compared between females and males (Figures 3B, S1B). Females reported higher
295 frequencies of neurocognitive and neurosensory symptoms, including loss of interest,
296 behavioral changes, depressive mood, slowed movements, and altered taste or smell. Of

297 these, persistent fatigue positively associated with female sex (Table S5). Symptoms such as
298 chest pain, nausea, and tremor were reported equally by both sexes (Figure 3B).

299 We next evaluated the influence of time since LC diagnosis and patient age on symptom
300 frequency. Females in our cohort had longer disease duration, with up to 60 months since
301 diagnosis, compared with males, whose maximum duration was 48 months. Females
302 diagnosed 37–60 months prior exhibited the highest symptom burden, whereas males with a
303 2-year diagnosis reported the most symptoms (Figures 3C–D). However, we did not find an
304 association between symptom burden and disease duration (Table S5). Symptom frequency
305 in females was highest between 61 and 70 years with persistent fatigue positively associating
306 with age (Table S5), while younger females reported fewer symptoms (Figures 3E–F). No
307 clear age-related pattern was observed in males (Figures 3E–F). It should be noted that no
308 male participants were included in the 61–70-year age group, which limits direct sex-based
309 comparisons within this age stratum. Among the 30 LC patients who responded, more than
310 half (63%) reported negative impacts on work (Figure S1C), with 53% of these indicating a
311 need to stop working entirely.

312 Overall, our results suggest that females with LC experience a higher symptom burden than
313 males, particularly for persistent fatigue, neurocognitive and neurosensory symptoms. In
314 females, symptom frequency increases with older age, whereas no clear age-related pattern
315 is observed in men. LC also substantially affects daily functioning, including work capacity.

316

317 **CD8⁺ T cells display sex differential cytotoxic phenotype in LC patients**

318 Although T cells play a critical role in SARS-CoV-2 clearance and recovery from COVID-19
319 [61–65], their involvement in LC remains unclear [66,67]. Some studies have reported T cell
320 alterations, including exhausted T cells [42], reduced CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ memory cells [42,68],
321 and elevated PD-1 expression on central memory cells [69], whereas others found no
322 differences in total CD4⁺ or CD8⁺ T cells or their memory compartments [66,70,71]. To
323 investigate cellular immune changes in LC, we phenotyped CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T cells by flow
324 cytometry and compared their profiles between controls and LC patients. CD4⁺ T cell profiles,

325 including memory subsets and activation markers, were also examined (Figures S2A, S3A–
326 E). Consistent with previous reports [66,70,71], total CD4⁺ T cell levels and activation status
327 were similar in controls and LC patients (Figures S3A–B). Memory subsets, defined by CCR7
328 and CD45RA expression, were also comparable between groups, including T effector memory
329 cells (CCR7⁺ CD45RA⁺, Figure S3C), T central memory cells (CCR7⁺ CD45RA⁺, Figure
330 S3D), and T memory cells re-expressing RA (CCR7⁺ CD45RA⁺, Figure S3E).

331 To characterize the cytotoxic profile of CD8⁺ T cells, we assessed expression of granzyme B
332 and K, perforin, and Natural Killer group 2 member D (NKG2D) by flow cytometry (Figure
333 S2B). Given that sex can influence LC presentation (Fig 3) and progression [41,42,72], we
334 disaggregated our analysis by sex (Figure 4A–E). The frequency of CD8⁺ T cells was slightly
335 increased in the LC group (Figure S4A), with sex-disaggregated analysis revealing that this
336 increase was driven by males (Figure 4A).

337 Examination of the cytotoxic profile showed no sex differences in granzyme B (Figure 4B) or
338 perforin (Figure 4D), and no significant differences were observed between controls and LC
339 patients (Figures S4E, S4G), consistent with previous reports [66,70]. Similarly, the
340 frequencies of CD8⁺ effector memory, central memory, and TEMRA subsets did not differ
341 significantly between groups (Figures S4B–D). Interestingly, the production of granzyme K by
342 CD8⁺ T cells was significantly decreased in LC patients, a change that appeared to be driven
343 primarily by females (Figures S4C, 4C), even though it did not reach statistical significance
344 (Table S6). Similarly, NKG2D expression was reduced in LC patients, with this reduction also
345 seemingly attributable to females (Figures S4H, 4E), even though statistical significance was
346 not reached (Table S6).

347 Next, we examined Natural Killer (NK) cells, which play a critical role in innate antiviral defense
348 and may become impaired during acute COVID-19, reducing their ability to eliminate infected
349 cells [73]. However, their role in post-acute infection, and particularly in LC, remains unclear
350 [68,73]. First, we assessed overall NK cell (Fig S2C) frequency consistent with previous
351 reports [68,73], we found no differences between controls and LC patients, [68,73] nor
352 between females and males (Figures S4I, 4F). As for the expression of granzyme B, granzyme

353 K, perforin, and NKG2D (Figures 4G–J, S4J–M) by NK cells, no significant differences were
354 observed between controls and LC patients for any of the cytotoxic markers (Table S7).
355 Lastly, we assessed humoral immunity, as antibodies generated after natural SARS-CoV-2
356 infection provide protection against reinfection [74,75], even though the role of B cells in LC is
357 still a subject of active research [76,77]. No significant differences were observed in total B
358 cells, memory B cells, or plasmablasts between groups (Figures S2D, S3F–H). Consistent
359 with prior studies [22,70,78], we found no differences in IgA, IgG, or IgM antibodies against
360 the Spike or Nucleocapsid proteins between controls and LC patients (Figures S3I–N).
361 Our results indicate that LC is associated with subtle, sex-specific alterations in CD8⁺ T cell
362 cytotoxic profile, particularly reduced granzyme K and NKG2D in women, while B cells, CD4⁺
363 T cells, NK cells, and humoral immunity remain largely unaffected. This highlights a potential
364 role for CD8⁺ T cell dysfunction in female patients as a contributor to persistent LC
365 pathophysiology.

366

367 **Long COVID patients exhibit sex-specific differences in systemic inflammatory profiles.**

368 Recent studies have sought to link specific markers of immune dysfunction and inflammation
369 with LC [79–82]. Cytokines such as interleukin (IL)-1 β , IL-6, tumor necrosis factor (TNF- α),
370 and interferon-gamma-inducible protein (IP-10) have been repeatedly associated with the
371 condition [83–87]. To investigate systemic inflammation in LC, we quantified plasma cytokines
372 in a sex-disaggregated manner. Consistent with prior reports [84,86,87], TNF- α levels were
373 elevated in LC patients (Figure S5A). Although TNF- α was also increased in females with LC
374 compared to female controls, the elevation was more pronounced in males (Figure 5A), but
375 without reaching statistical significance (Table S8). In contrast, anti-inflammatory IL-10 levels
376 did not differ significantly between groups (Figures 5B, S5B). sCD40L, a marker linked to
377 inflammation [88] and vascular risk [89], was elevated in LC patient serum, with the increase
378 predominantly observed in females (Figures 5C, S5C). However, it did not reach statistical
379 significance (Table S8). Soluble Fas (sFAS) has been detected in the serum of COVID-19
380 patients, with levels correlating with disease severity [90]. In our cohort, sFAS levels were

381 modestly increased in LC patients, driven primarily by females, who showed higher circulating
382 sFAS than female controls (Figures 5D, S5D), without reaching statistical significance (Table
383 S8). As for the plasma levels of IL-6, IL-1b, IFN- γ , MCP-1, IL-18, and IL-23 they were similar
384 between controls and LC groups (Figure S5 H-M)

385 To examine the cytotoxic profile in LC patients, we measured plasma concentrations of
386 perforin and granzymes A and B. Serum perforin was reduced in LC patients, driven by
387 females, whereas granzymes A and B levels remained unchanged across groups and sexes
388 (Figures 5E–G, S5E–G, Table S8).

389 Next, we investigated whether the time elapsed between LC diagnosis and sample collection
390 influenced plasma levels of cytokines, soluble factors, or granzymes by performing correlation
391 analyses (Figures S5H–M). Interestingly, TNF- α , IL-10, sCD40L, sFAS, and granzyme A
392 showed no correlation with disease duration (Figures S5H–K, S5M). Perforin was the only
393 factor displaying a positive correlation, with levels increasing in patients with longer disease
394 duration, although the correlation was modest (Figure S5L).

395 Collectively, our results suggest that LC is associated with a sex-differential inflammatory
396 profile. TNF- α levels are elevated, particularly in males, while females show increased
397 sCD40L and sFAS, alongside reduced perforin, further supporting a potential impairment of
398 cytotoxic function (Fig 4C). Other immune mediators, including IL-10 and granzymes A and B,
399 remain unchanged.

400

401 **Discussion**

402 LC is an emerging syndrome, affecting around 65 million people worldwide [6,7]. The world
403 has been confronted with new SARS-CoV-2 variants, leading to repeated infections [91] and
404 conducting to a high prevalence of LC [92]. Due to LC heterogeneity, the plethora of relapsing
405 and remitting symptoms [93] and multisystemic organ involvement [10,11], the exact
406 mechanisms underpinning LC pathophysiology and long-term prognosis remain unclear.
407 Here, we sought to contribute to filling this knowledge gap, by studying a cohort of 34 patients
408 with LC. In our cohort, females experienced a higher symptom burden, particularly persistent

409 fatigue and neurocognitive and neurosensory manifestations, alongside a propensity for
410 greater comorbidity load, which increased with age. Males, in contrast, tended to display
411 stronger systemic inflammatory signals, notably elevated TNF- α , but fewer symptoms overall.
412 Immune profiling revealed sex-dependent alterations in the cytotoxic profile of CD8⁺ T cells,
413 with females showing a tendency for reduced granzyme K and NKG2D expression, increased
414 sCD40L and sFAS, and decreased perforin, while other lymphocyte populations and humoral
415 responses remained largely unaffected. These findings highlight potentially distinct pathogenic
416 mechanisms in males and females and underscore the need for sex-tailored approaches in
417 the management and study of LC.

418 The exact etiology of LC remains unclear, but several risk factors, including female sex, age,
419 comorbidities, and lower socioeconomic status, have been identified [12,13,32,33]. Consistent
420 with these associations, LC patients in our cohort had a propensity for higher number of
421 comorbidities than controls, with females showing the greatest burden. Co-morbidities
422 affecting females were enriched in the endocrine, metabolic, psychological, and circulatory
423 systems, which may exacerbate disease through sustained inflammation, oxidative stress,
424 and organ dysfunction. These comorbidities likely contribute both to the onset and persistence
425 of LC, in line with previous studies [12,13,55–57]. Symptom analysis revealed that females
426 reported higher frequencies of chronic fatigue among other neurocognitive and neurosensory
427 complaints, such as drowsiness, concentration deficits, and altered taste or smell, consistent
428 with prior observations [42,94]. The pattern of neurocognitive and neurosensory symptoms
429 resembles myalgic encephalomyelitis/chronic fatigue syndrome (ME/CFS), a condition
430 characterized by severe fatigue, post-exertional malaise, and cognitive impairment, with a
431 female-to-male prevalence ratio of approximately 4:1 [95]. Viral infections, such as by Epstein-
432 Barr virus, have been implicated in ME/CFS, and emerging evidence suggests that SARS-
433 CoV-2 may similarly trigger ME/CFS in a subset of patients [96]. Moreover, symptom burden
434 in females increased both age and tendentially with longer disease duration, whereas males
435 showed no clear age- or duration-dependent patterns, emphasizing the need for sex- and

436 duration-specific management strategies. Importantly, more than half of responding patients
437 reported negative impacts on work, with many needing to stop working entirely, highlighting
438 the substantial functional and socioeconomic burden of LC.

439 Our immune profiling revealed subtle but sex-specific alterations in CD8⁺ T cell cytotoxic
440 profile in LC patients. While total CD8⁺ T cell levels tended to be slightly increased in males,
441 females exhibited a propensity for reduced granzyme K and NKG2D expression, which might
442 indicate impaired cytotoxic function. The overall increase in CD8⁺ T cells in patients may
443 reflect ongoing immune responses against a persistent SARS-CoV-2 reservoir in multiple
444 organs, as these cells are essential for viral clearance [97]. Alternatively, it is also possible
445 that other chronic viral infections may contribute to sustained CD8⁺ T-cell activation and
446 expansion of effector populations, particularly in older adults. Prior work has shown that LC
447 symptoms, such as fatigue and neurocognitive dysfunction, at a median of four months post-
448 diagnosis were independently associated with serological evidence of recent EBV reactivation
449 or elevated EBNA IgG levels, but not with ongoing EBV viremia [98]. Interestingly, prior CMV
450 infection appeared protective against neurocognitive LC [98], suggesting that antigenic burden
451 and immune imprinting from latent infections may modulate clinical outcomes. Moreover,
452 associations between LC and VZV reactivation have also been reported [99]. These
453 observations underscore the complexity of immune activation in LC and highlight the need for
454 future studies to incorporate comprehensive assessments of latent viral co-infections (e.g.,
455 CMV, EBV, VZV) and their potential synergistic or antagonistic effects on T-cell phenotypes
456 and symptom persistence. The fact that the increase in CD8⁺ T cell frequency tended to be
457 driven primarily by males may help explain why male sex is not a major risk factor for
458 developing LC. NKG2D, a key activating receptor on CD8⁺ T and NK cells, acts as a co-
459 stimulatory molecule in CD8⁺ T cells, enhancing cytotoxicity and contributing to long-term
460 memory formation [100,101]. Blockade of NKG2D has been shown to impair memory CD8⁺
461 T cell development [102]. In our cohort, despite the higher total CD8⁺ T cell counts, LC
462 patients, particularly females, tendentially showed reduced NKG2D granzyme K expression,

463 and perforin levels in the plasma. These alterations may indicate differences in CD8⁺ T cell
464 functional capacity that could contribute to less efficient clearance of infected cells and
465 potentially influence the development of long-term memory T cells. Although LC patients
466 exhibited a trend toward reduced central memory CD8⁺ T cells compared to controls, this
467 difference did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.09$). These findings suggest that any
468 impairment in CD8⁺ memory formation may be subtle and not readily detectable in cohorts of
469 this size. Future studies incorporating larger sample sizes and additional functional markers,
470 such as PD-1, TOX, TIM-3, and TIGIT, will be essential to clarify whether CD8⁺ T-cell
471 exhaustion or memory dysregulation contributes to the immunopathology of LC. While plasma
472 perforin does not directly reflect cellular cytotoxicity, several studies have nonetheless
473 reported associations between plasma perforin levels and clinical outcomes influenced by
474 cytotoxic immune activity, including responses to cancer therapies [103] and chronic hepatitis
475 B treatment [104]. Plasma perforin has also been proposed as a serologic marker of clinical
476 stage in virus-induced severe fever with thrombocytopenia syndrome [105]. Consistent with
477 previous studies, we observed no differences in the frequency of CD4⁺ T cells or in their
478 memory subsets [70,71]. Yet, the specific role of these cells in LC etiology is still to be clarified
479 [66,67], as other authors have found alterations in central memory and exhausted profile
480 [42,68,69]. NK cells, critical components of the innate antiviral response, displayed no
481 significant differences in overall frequency or cytotoxic marker expression (granzyme B,
482 granzyme K, perforin, NKG2D) between LC patients and controls, or between sexes. This
483 suggests that, in contrast to CD8⁺ T cells, NK cell cytotoxic profile is largely preserved in LC.
484 Similarly, humoral immunity appeared intact. No differences were observed in total B cells,
485 memory B cells, plasmablasts, or in antibody responses (IgA, IgG, IgM) against SARS-CoV-2
486 Spike and Nucleocapsid proteins between LC patients and controls. Indicating that LC is not
487 associated with major deficits in the B cell compartment or antibody-mediated immunity. These
488 findings may suggest a potential role for CD8⁺ T cell dysfunction in the pathophysiology of
489 LC, particularly in female patients.

490 Systemic inflammatory markers also tended to exhibit sex-specific patterns. TNF- α levels were
491 elevated predominantly in males, whereas females showed increased sCD40L and sFAS
492 alongside with reduced perforin. Unlike other chronic infection-associated conditions such as
493 ME/CFS, where TNF- α declines after 2–3 years [106], TNF- α levels in LC remained stable
494 over disease duration. Soluble CD40L levels displayed a propensity to be elevated in LC
495 patients, reflecting patterns seen in autoimmune and inflammatory diseases, where sCD40L
496 amplifies systemic inflammation [88,107–109] and can disrupt the blood-brain barrier [109].
497 Similarly, increased sFAS, which can interfere with apoptosis and the clearance of damaged
498 or infected cells [90], suggests ongoing immune activation in women and may further
499 exacerbate chronic symptoms. Together, these observations indicate that LC might be
500 associated with systemic inflammation and cytotoxic dysfunction, with sex-specific patterns
501 that may underlie the female bias in symptom severity and neurological manifestations.

502 Understanding the mechanisms driving LC will not only advance LC research but also provide
503 valuable insights into other infection-associated chronic conditions, including ME/CFS and
504 chronic Lyme disease. Our findings add to the growing evidence that sex-differential immunity
505 plays a key role in shaping disease trajectories, highlighting the urgent need for tailored
506 therapeutic strategies.

507 This study has several limitations. The major one is that our LC cohort was relatively small
508 and lacked ethnic and racial diversity, which places some constraints in the robustness of our
509 observations and may contribute to explain the modest results of our linear and logistic
510 regression analysis. In addition, baseline clinical parameters prior to acute infection were not
511 available, limiting our ability to assess pre-existing differences. The absence of male
512 participants in the 61–70-year age group represents a limitation when interpreting age-
513 stratified symptom comparisons between sexes. This imbalance may introduce bias in
514 assessing sex-related differences within older cohorts and restricts the generalizability of our
515 findings. Future studies should aim to recruit more balanced cohorts across age and sex strata
516 to enable robust stratified analyses and minimize potential confounding effects. Another

517 limitation is the potential limitation by patients to attend healthcare consultations, due to severe
518 illness, reduced mobility, or social exclusion, were not captured, which may have introduced
519 selection bias. Despite these limitations, our study provides a detailed, sex-disaggregated
520 characterization of LC patients, combining clinical, immunological, and inflammatory profiling.
521 Lastly, we must acknowledge the potential confounding role of comorbidities in shaping
522 immune signatures and the subsequent limitations of fully disentangling LC-specific effects
523 from comorbidity-driven influences. Nonetheless, the inclusion of a well-matched SARS-CoV-
524 2–infected control group strengthens our comparative analyses. Moreover, by examining long-
525 term LC patients, some with symptoms persisting over four years, we offer unique insights into
526 chronic disease mechanisms, immune dysfunction, and sex-specific differences that can
527 inform future therapeutic strategies.

528

529 **Perspectives and Significance**

530 Our findings highlight the complex, sex-specific nature of LC. Together, these results
531 emphasize the need for sex- and duration-specific management strategies, the identification
532 of robust biomarkers, and the development of personalized therapies targeting distinct LC
533 endotypes. Our results provide mechanistic insights into symptom persistence and immune
534 dysregulation, highlighting females' heightened vulnerability. Looking forward, these insights
535 could inform the design of clinical trials by encouraging sex-stratified analyses and testing
536 therapies that restore cytotoxic T cell function, including immunomodulatory or antiviral
537 strategies.

538

539 **Conclusions**

540 Females tended to exhibit heightened symptom burden, particularly neurocognitive and
541 neurosensory complaints, which increase with age and disease duration, whereas men show
542 no clear age- or duration-dependent patterns. Comorbidities, especially affecting endocrine,
543 metabolic, and circulatory systems, likely exacerbate these symptoms through sustained
544 inflammation and organ dysfunction. At the immune level, we observed subtle sex differences:

545 women with LC had a propensity to display reduced CD8⁺ T cell cytotoxic function, lower
546 NKG2D and granzyme K expression, increased sCD40L and sFAS, and decreased perforin,
547 whereas men show elevated TNF- α levels. These molecular signatures may contribute to
548 symptom persistence, immune dysregulation, and neurological manifestations in women.
549 Importantly, over half of patients reported functional impairments affecting work capacity,
550 underscoring the socioeconomic burden of LC. By integrating clinical, immunological, and
551 inflammatory profiling in a sex-disaggregated manner, this work emphasizes the importance
552 of personalized, sex- age- and duration-specific management strategies.

553

554 **Declarations**

555 **Ethics approval and consent to participate**

556 All procedures were approved by NOVA Medical School ethics committee (178/2024/CEFCM)
557 and by ethics committee for health from ARSLVT (2508/CES/2023), in accordance with the
558 provisions of the Declaration of Helsinki and the Good Clinical Practice guidelines of the
559 International Conference on Harmonization. All the participants signed the informed consent
560 at the time of enrolment in the study and completed the clinical survey.

561

562 **Consent for publication**

563 All participants sign the informed consent for publication.

564

565 **Availability of data and materials**

566 The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the
567 corresponding author on reasonable request.

568

569 **Competing interests**

570 The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

571

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582

583 **Authors' contributions**

584 JF, JG, CC, MG and MIN designed and performed experiments and analyzed the data. JF
585 enrolled the subjects and collected demographic data. JB conceived the statistical analysis.
586 JG wrote the first draft of the manuscript. HS conceptualized the study, designed experiments,
587 analyzed the data, supervised the project and wrote the final version of the manuscript. All
588 authors read and approved the final manuscript.

589

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597 experimental support and Hugo Vicente Miranda for reagents.

598

599 **Figure legends**

600 **Figure 1- Characterization of study participants.**

601 **(A)** Outline of participant recruitment, divided in 2 groups: controls (Ctr, orange) consisting of
602 7 males and 19 females, and Long COVID patients (LC, purple) consisting of 10 males and
603 24 females.

604 **(B)** Distribution of Ctr (left) and LC (right) across the age intervals: <30 years old (yo), 30-50
605 yo, 51-60 yo, 61-70 yo and >70 yo.

606 **(C)** Cumulative distribution of Body Mass Index (BMI) in Ctr (n= 26, orange) and LC patients
607 (n= 34, purple).

608 **(D)** Cumulative distribution of BMI disaggregated by sex in Ctr (left; females n= 19, males n=
609 7) and LC patients (right; females n= 24, males n= 10).

610 **(E)** Number of SARS-CoV2 PCR-positive tests in Ctr (n= 26, orange) and LC patients (n= 34,
611 purple).

612 **(F)** Elapsed time (in months) between primary infection and sample collection in Ctr (n= 21,
613 orange) and LC patients (n= 34, purple).

614 **(G)** Number of COVID-19 vaccines doses received by Ctr (n= 26, orange) and LC patients (n=
615 34, purple).

616 **(H)** Elapsed time (months) between the first COVID-19 vaccine dose and sample collection in
617 Ctr (n= 24, orange) and LC patients (n= 32, purple).

618 p values *p < 0.05, **p<0.01; ns, not significant determined by non-parametric Mann-Whitney
619 test (C, D, F-H) and by parametric unpaired t test (C, D). Effect sizes for all graphs are reported
620 in Tables S9 and S10.

621

622 **Figure 2- Sex-disaggregated comorbidities in persistent Long COVID patients.**

623 (A) Number of comorbidities in Ctr (n= 26) and in LC (n= 34).
 624 (B) Number of comorbidities in females (Ctr n= 19, LC n= 24) and in males (Ctr n= 7, LC
 625 n=10).
 626 (C) Frequency of comorbidities in Ctr by health system. MS: Musculoskeletal System, DS:
 627 Digestive System, GS: Genital System, RS: Respiratory System, NS: Neurological System,
 628 CS: Circulatory System, P: Psychological, EMNS: Endocrine, Metabolic and Nutritional
 629 System. Females (n= 19) and Males (n= 7).
 630 (D) As in C, for LC. Females (n= 24) and males (n= 10).
 631 Data represents mean \pm SD. p values *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01; ns, not significant determined by
 632 non-parametric Mann-Whitney test (A, B) and by parametric unpaired t test (B). Effect sizes
 633 for all graphs are reported in Tables S9 and S10.

634

635 **Figure 3- Sex-disaggregated symptomatology in persistent Long COVID patients.**

636 (A) Symptom burden of LC patients disaggregated by sex. Females (n= 21) and males (n=9).
 637 (B) Sex-disaggregated symptom frequency by category: Neurocognitive, Neurosensory,
 638 Respiratory System and Cardiothoracic (RS/CT), Digestive System (DS), Musculoskeletal
 639 System (MS) and Fatigue, Dermatological (D), Sexual (S) and Others.
 640 (C) Frequency of symptoms in LC females stratified by the elapsed time (months) between
 641 sample collection and diagnosis.
 642 (D) As in C, for LC males.
 643 (E) Age-wise distribution of symptoms in LC females.
 644 (F) As in E, for LC males.

645 p value *p < 0.05 determined by parametric unpaired t test (A). Effect sizes for all graphs are
 646 reported in Table S9.

647

648 **Figure 4- Sex-disaggregated cytotoxic response in persistent Long COVID patients.**

649 (A) Frequency of CD8⁺ T cells in females (left; Ctr n= 15, LC n= 20) and males (right; Ctr n=
 650 6, LC n= 9).

651 (B) Frequency of CD8⁺Granzyme B⁺ cells in females (left; Ctr n= 15, LC n= 20) and males
652 (right; Ctr n= 6, LC n= 9).

653 (C) Frequency of CD8⁺Granzyme K⁺ cells in females (left; Ctr n= 15, LC n= 20) and males
654 (right; Ctr n= 5, LC n= 9).

655 (D) Frequency of CD8⁺Perforin⁺ cells in females (left; Ctr n= 14, LC n= 19) and males (right;
656 Ctr n= 6, LC n= 9).

657 (E) Frequency of CD8⁺NKG2D⁺ cells in females (left; Ctr n= 15, LC n= 20) and males (right;
658 Ctr n= 6, LC n= 9).

659 (F) Frequency of CD56⁺ cells in females (left; Ctr n= 15, LC n= 18) and males (right; Ctr n= 6,
660 LC n= 9).

661 (G) Frequency of CD56⁺Granzyme B⁺ cells in females (left; Ctr n= 15, LC n= 18) and males
662 (right; Ctr n= 6, LC n= 8).

663 (H) Frequency of CD56⁺Granzyme K⁺ cells in females (left; Ctr n= 15, LC n= 18) and males
664 (right; Ctr n= 5, LC n= 8).

665 (I) Frequency of CD56⁺Perforin⁺ cells in females (left; Ctr n= 14, LC n= 17) and males (right;
666 Ctr n= 6, LC n= 8).

667 (J) Frequency of CD56⁺NKG2D⁺ cells in females (left; Ctr n= 15, LC n= 18) and males (right;
668 Ctr n= 6, LC n= 8).

669 Data represents mean \pm SD for parametric tests, or median \pm IQR for nonparametric tests. p
670 values *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01; ns, not significant determined by parametric unpaired t test (A-H,
671 J) and by non-parametric Mann-Whitney test (E, F, I, J). Effect sizes for all graphs are reported
672 in Tables S9 and S10.

673

674 **Figure 5- Sex-disaggregated inflammatory plasma profile in Long COVID patients.**

675 (A) Plasma concentration of TNF- α (pg/ml) in females (left; Ctr n= 16, LC n= 23) and males
676 (right; Ctr n= 6, LC n= 9).

677 (B) Plasma concentration of IL-10 (pg/ml) in females (left; Ctr n= 18, LC n= 23) and males
678 (right; Ctr n= 6, LC n= 9).

679 (C) Plasma concentration of sCD40L (pg/ml) in females (left; Ctr n= 18, LC n= 22) and males
680 (right; Ctr n= 6, LC n= 9).

681 (D) Plasma concentration of sFAS (pg/ml) in females (left; Ctr n= 18, LC n= 23) and males
682 (right; Ctr n= 6, LC n= 9).

683 (E) Plasma concentration of Perforin (pg/ml) in females (left; Ctr n= 17, LC n= 23) and males
684 (right; Ctr n= 6, LC n= 9).

685 (F) Plasma concentration of Granzyme A (pg/ml) in females (left; Ctr n= 18, LC n= 23) and
686 males (right; Ctr n= 6, LC n= 9).

687 (G) Plasma concentration of Granzyme B (pg/ml) in females (left; Ctr n= 18, LC n= 23) and
688 males (right; Ctr n= 6, LC n= 9).

689 Data represents mean \pm SD for parametric tests, or median \pm IQR for nonparametric tests. p
690 values *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01; ns, not significant determined by non-parametric Mann-Whitney
691 test (A-G) and by parametric unpaired t test (C, E, G). Effect sizes for all graphs are reported
692 in Tables S9 and S10.

693

694 **Figure S1- Frequency of symptoms in Long COVID patients.**

695 (A) Frequency of symptoms of LC patients.

696 (B) Frequency of symptoms disaggregated by sex (females, pink; males, blue).

697 (C) Work-related impacts of LC.

698

699 **Figure S2- Flow cytometric gating strategy.**

700 (A) Gating strategy for activated and memory CD4⁺ T cell subsets.

701 (B) Gating strategy for Granzyme B⁺, Granzyme K⁺, Perforin⁺ and NKG2D⁺ CD8⁺ T cells and
702 memory CD8⁺ T cell subsets.

703 (C) Gating strategy for Granzyme B⁺, Granzyme K⁺, Perforin⁺ and NKG2D⁺ CD56⁺ cells.

704 (D) Gating strategy for CD19⁺CD3⁺CD27⁺ and CD19⁺CD3⁺CD27⁺CD38⁺ B cells.

705

706 **Figure S3- Humoral and cellular responses in Long COVID.**

707 (A) Frequency of CD4⁺ T cells in Ctr (n= 20) and LCs (n= 15).

708 (B) Frequency of CD4⁺ CD38⁺ T cells in Ctr (n= 19) and LCs (n= 13).

709 (C) Frequency of CD4⁺ T effector memory (TEM) cells in Ctr (n= 15) and LCs (n= 8).

710 (D) Frequency of CD4⁺ T central memory (TCM) cells in Ctr (n= 15) and LCs (n= 8).

711 (E) Frequency of CD4⁺ TMRA cells in Ctr (n= 15) and LCs (n= 8).

712 (F) Frequency of circulating B cells in Ctr (n= 20) and LCs (n= 15).

713 (G) Frequency of memory B cells in Ctr (n= 20) and LCs (n= 11).

714 (H) Frequency of plasmablasts B cells in Ctr (n= 19) and LCs (n= 13).

715 (I) Anti-spike IgA endpoint titer (Ctr n=26; n=34).

716 (J) Anti-spike IgG endpoint titer (Ctr n=26; LC n=34).

717 (K) Anti-spike IgM endpoint titer (Ctr n=26; LC n=34).

718 (L) Anti-Nucleocapsid IgA endpoint titer (Ctr n=26; LC n=34).

719 (M) Anti-spike IgG endpoint titer (Ctr n=26; LC n=34).

720 (N) Anti-spike IgM endpoint titer (Ctr n=26; LC n=34).

721 Data represents mean \pm SD for parametric tests, or median \pm IQR for nonparametric tests. nd:

722 not detectable; p values ns, not significant determined by parametric unpaired t test (A, C, D)

723 and by non-parametric Mann-Whitney test (B, E-N). Effect sizes for all graphs are reported in

724 Tables S9 and S10.

725

726 **Figure S4- CD8⁺ T cell and NK cell characterization in controls and Long COVID**
727 **patients.**

728 (A) Frequency of CD8⁺ T cells in Ctr (n= 21) and LC (n= 29).

729 (B) Frequency of CD8⁺ T effector memory (TEM) cells in Ctr (n= 21) and LCs (n= 26).

730 (C) Frequency of CD8⁺ T central memory (TCM) cells in Ctr (n= 21) and LCs (n= 26).

731 (D) Frequency of CD8⁺ TMRA cells in Ctr (n= 21) and LCs (n= 26).

732 (E) Frequency of CD8⁺Granzyme B⁺ cells in Ctr (n= 21) and LC (n= 29).

733 (F) Frequency of CD8⁺Granzyme K⁺ cells in Ctr (n= 20) and LC (n= 29).

734 (G) Frequency of CD8⁺Perforin⁺ cells in Ctr (n= 20) and LC (n= 28).

735 (H) Frequency of CD8⁺ NKG2D⁺ cells in Ctr (n= 21) and LC (n= 29).

736 (I) Frequency of CD56⁺ cells in Ctr (n= 21) and LC (n= 27).

737 (J) Frequency of CD56⁺Granzyme B⁺ cells in Ctr (n= 21) and LC (n= 26).

738 (K) Frequency of CD56⁺Granzyme K⁺ cells in Ctr (n= 20) and LC (n= 26).

739 (L) Frequency of CD56⁺Perforin⁺ cells in Ctr (n= 20) and LC (n= 25).

740 (M) Frequency of CD56⁺ NKG2D⁺ cells in Ctr (n= 21) and LC (n= 26).

741 Data represents mean \pm SD for parametric tests, or median \pm IQR for nonparametric tests. p
 742 values *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01; ns, not significant determined by parametric unpaired t test (A,
 743 B, D-G, J, K, M) and by non-parametric Mann-Whitney test (C, H, I, L). Effect sizes for all
 744 graphs are reported in Tables S9 and S10.

745

746 **Figure S5- Inflammatory plasma profile in controls and persistent Long COVID patients.**

747 (A) Plasma concentration of TNF- α (pg/ml) in Ctr (n= 22) and LC (n= 32).

748 (B) Plasma concentration of IL-10 (pg/ml) in Ctr (n= 24) and LC (n= 32).

749 (C) Plasma concentration of sCD40L (pg/ml) in Ctr (n= 24) and LC (n= 30).

750 (D) Plasma concentration of sFAS (pg/ml) in Ctr (n= 24) and LC (n= 32).

751 (E) Plasma concentration of Perforin (pg/ml) in Ctr (n= 24) and LC (n= 32).

752 (F) Plasma concentration of Granzyme A (pg/ml) in Ctr (n= 24) and LC (n= 32).

753 (G) Plasma concentration of Granzyme B (pg/ml) in Ctr (n= 24) and LC (n= 32).

754 (H) Plasma concentration of IL-1 β (pg/ml) in Ctr (n= 20) and LC (n= 32).

755 (I) Plasma concentration of IFN- γ (pg/ml) in Ctr (n= 24) and LC (n= 32).

756 (J) Plasma concentration of MCP-1 (pg/ml) in Ctr (n= 18) and LC (n= 21).

757 (K) Plasma concentration of IL-6 (pg/ml) in Ctr (n= 23) and LC (n= 32).

758 (L) Plasma concentration of IL-18 (pg/ml) in Ctr (n= 24) and LC (n= 32).

759 (M) Plasma concentration of IL-23 (pg/ml) in Ctr (n= 24) and LC (n= 32).

760 (N) Correlation between plasma TNF- α concentration (pg/mL) and elapsed time (months)
761 between LC diagnosis and sample collection (n = 32).

762 (O) As in H for IL-10 (n= 32).

763 (P) As in H for sCD40L (n= 30).

764 (Q) As in H for sFAS (n= 32).

765 (R) As in H for Perforin (n= 32).

766 (S) As in H for Granzyme A (n= 32).

767 Data represents median \pm IQR for nonparametric tests. p values *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01,
768 ***p<0.0001; ns, not significant determined by non-parametric Mann-Whitney test (A-M).
769 Spearman correlation (N-S). Effect sizes for all graphs are reported in Table S9.

770

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Figure 1

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Figure 2

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Figure 3

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Figure 5

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Figure Supplemental 1

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Figure Supplemental 2

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Figure Supplemental 3

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Figure Supplemental 5

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